

ICT skills among the research scholars in the academic institutions of Thoothukudi District A SURVEY

Dr.S.Gandhimathi

Librarian, G,Venkataswamy Naidu College ,Kovilpatti

Corresponding author- **Dr.S.Gandhimathi**

Email-rsgndhi1977@gmail.com

Abstract

Technology has a significant impact on today's higher education system. The use of computers and other ICTs for research and teaching therefore requires that research scholars have the requisite abilities. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how well-versed and how frequently research scholars in Thoothukudi District academic institutions use information and communication technologies (ICTs). To gather information and raise awareness regarding ICT skills and talents, data was gathered for this purpose from M.Phil. and Ph.D. researchers. The study demonstrates that numerous fundamental Microsoft Office (Excel & Word) approaches, which are more important and valuable, are not well known by the majority of research scholars. A questionnaire with open-ended and one closed-ended question served as the basis for the investigation. The study was designed to investigate the challenges respondents encountered when using online search engines and information communication technologies. Suggestions are made for research students to use ICT infrastructure to its fullest potential.

Keywords: ICT, research scholars, survey, skills

Introduction

The world is undergoing a massive information and communication technology revolution, and developing nations like India are no exception. Information and communication technology have brought about new approaches to research and teaching, as well as being integrated into educational facilities for online learning. Research academics in India must pay for time spent using the Internet, whether in a cyber café or at the library, whereas some college communities in other nations enjoy free or quick access (some libraries provide free access). Researchers must demonstrate how they use ICT in their research in order to improve ICT services in the library. In order to improve ICT abilities, information and communication technologies have led to new ways of structuring the teaching environment in higher education and new directions in research.

In the current dynamic context, the significance of ICT in higher education needs to be stressed. The usage of new, developing ICTs in education makes it simple and quick to access a variety of global information resources. In reality, imagining a higher education setting with information technology is simple. As a result, a study on ICT proficiency among research researchers in Thoothukudi District academic institutions has been initiated.

Literature Review

Eze, Sunday C et al (2012), have made an effort to examine the influencing elements for government-owned universities in Nigeria to adopt information and communication technology (ICT). To determine the adoption of ICT in Nigerian colleges, they have identified 13 criteria. Using the

purposive strategy, 30 senior executives were selected as the sample group. Government universities have not yet fully tapped into the possibilities of ICT, it was discovered. The minimal utility of ICT was due to several anomalies and inadequate internet access, which were both legitimate causes.

Khan, S., Bhatti, & Khan, A. (2011) It is advised that professors employ ICT in their lectures for efficient learning. Due to a lack of available instruction, the majority of respondents frequently consult the internet. They were unable to employ sophisticated search methods, and they had trouble locating pertinent literature. Because they were unaware of databases, the majority of library users turned to search engines. The majority of users are not familiar with e-books, open access books, or journals. The availability of computer laboratories is likewise limited and does not meet user needs.

Adeyoyin, Samuel Olu (2005) conducted a study on the level of ICT literacy among Nigerian working librarians. To evaluate the quality of librarians and determine how well-versed in ICT they were, a questionnaire approach was used. For the study, librarians from 18 universities in Nigeria were chosen. ICT illiteracy was present in 68% (approx) of the survey participants and about 32% of the respondents. The researcher made an effort to close the gap between the current situation and the required level of ICT literacy.

Al – Ansari, Husain (2011) conducted a survey on ICT applications in Kuwaiti special libraries. Several libraries were found to not be fully automated. Nonetheless, 25% of libraries use manual processes. The challenges to implementing ICT-enabled services in libraries were a lack of

skilled staff and poorly prioritised ICT programmes. The author suggested allocating funding for creating such an environment. Identification of the potential skills of LIS professionals and placement of them suitably become essential. The crew will be prepared to work efficiently thanks to routine training programmes.

Husain, Shabahat and Nazim, Mohammad (2015) attempt to research the impact of information and communication technologies in Indian university libraries. They distributed questionnaires to a few libraries, and 50% of them responded. Libraries were using traditional ICT solutions, which called into question the professionalism and qualitative perspectives of librarians. There were few instances of knowledge generation and sharing using platforms like blogs, wikis, RSS feeds, and social networking.

Objectives of the Study

The major goal of this study is to determine how well-versed and proficient the research scholars in the academic institutions of Thoothukudi District are in using computers and ICT for learning and conducting research.

1. To help respondents understand the importance of online resources.
2. To some extent encourage ICT usage.

Methodology

Based on the goals of the study and the questions to be answered, a schedule of questionnaires was created. The questions included the following topics: the profile of the respondents, their attitudes towards ICT, how they used ICT and what skills they had, how they could obtain online research information, and any issues they had. The inclusion of close-ended questions, check lists, and rating scales helped quantify and analyse the data. In the Thoothukudi District, 130 academic institutes conducting research were randomly chosen, and among them, questionnaires were given out. 120 of those questionnaires were returned and were discovered to be complete.

Data Analysis and Discussion

The analysis of data is the last step in the research process. The raw data and important findings that support conclusions are connected. This analysis method ought to be result oriented.

Table 3.1 Gender wise Frequency

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	53	44.17
Female	67	55.83
Total	120	100

Male i.e n=53 and female Gender i.e n=67 Most of the respondents were female.

Table 3.2 Age wise Frequency

AGE GROUP	Frequency	Percentage
21-25	58	48.33
26-30	45	37.50
Above 30	17	14.17
Total	120	100

Most of the respondents i.e n=58, were between the age of 21-25, the respondents i.e n=45 were in the age group of 26-30, respondents n=17 were above 30 years of age.

Table 3.3 Department wise Frequency

Department	Frequency	Percentage
Science	71	59.17
Social Sciences	49	40.83

Most of the respondents i.e.n=71, were under Science stream.

Table 3.4 Locality of Residence

Locality	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	63	52.50
Semi Urban	17	14.17
Urban	40	33.33
Total	120	100

More than half of the scholars i.e n=63 were living in rural area and one-third of the respondents i.e n=40 were living in urban area.

Table 3.5 Qualification wise Frequency

Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
M.Phil	95	79.17
Ph.D	25	20.83
Total	120	100

Most of the respondents i.e n=95 were M.Phil students.

Figure 3.5.1

Table 3.6 Usage of Computer

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Own computer	110	91.6
Others	10	8.3
Total	120	100

Most of the scholar i.e n=110 use own computer / laptop for research purposes.

Table 3.7 Internet Connectivity

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
YES	85	70.83
NO	35	29.16
TOTAL	120	100

More than 70% of the scholars are having own internet connection for using research activity.

Descriptive Statistics

Mean	60
Standard Error	2
Median	60
Standard Deviation	2.828427
Sample Variance	8
Range	4
Minimum	58
Maximum	62
Sum	120
Count	2
Largest(1)	62
Smallest(1)	58

The above table presents the descriptive statistics as, the standard error is 2 and standard deviation is 2.83. It is clearly found that the most of the

respondents were utilizing the internet for their research purpose only.

Table 3.8 Use of Mobile

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	62	51.67
No	58	48.33
Total	120	100

More than half of the scholars i.e n=62 were using mobile for research purposes.

Table 3.9 Purpose of Using Internet

S.No	Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Research purpose	45	33.33
2.	E-Mail	110	16.67
3.	Downloading E-resources	30	25.00
4.	Online Shopping	10	04.17
5.	Assignment	7	05.83
6.	Chatting	5	04.17
7.	All the above	13	10.83
	Total	220	100%

Results shows that out of 220 respondents were half using internet for e-mail and 45 respondents (20.45 of the respondents that is 110 (50 percent) are percentage) customs the internet for research

Figure 3.9.1 Purpose of using internet

Table 3.10 Preferred Search Engine

S.No	Search Engine	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Google	70	58.33
2.	Yahoo	20	16.67
3.	Ask.com	10	8.33
4.	Duck	7	5.83
5.	Bing	5	5
6.	AOL	4	3.33
7.	Others	3	2.50
	Total	120	100

The majority of the respondents i.e n=70 use Google search engine followed by Yahoo search engine with 20.

Table 3.11 Usefulness of the Internet

S.No	Opinion	Research without Internet			After using internet		
		Male	female	total	Male	Female	Total
1	Effective	16	10	24	47	57	84
2	Ineffective	37	51	86	6	10	16
3	Total	53	67	120	53	67	120

The Table illustrates the stark contrast between using the internet for research before and after. Of the 220 respondents, the majority of 37 men and the

majority of 57 women both agree that research is more productive when it is conducted using internet resources.

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances	Before using Internet	After using Internet
Mean	13	52
Variance	18	50
Observations	2	2
Pooled Variance	34	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	2	
t Stat	-6.68844	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.010816	
t Critical one-tail	2.919986	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.021631	
t Critical two-tail	4.302653	

The estimated value is more than the test statistic, which is -6.688, hence the null hypothesis is not rejected. Null Hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Between before and after the usage of the internet for research work, there is no meaningful association. It demonstrates that pupils

Table 3.12 ICT Facilities recommended by Research Scholars

S.No	Facilities	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Internet connected Personal Computer	40	33.33
2.	Internet connected laptop	30	25.00
3.	Digital library	18	15.00
4.	Photocopy and Scanner	13	10.83
5.	Multimedia projector	14	11.67
6.	Tele / Video Conferencing	5	04.17
	Total	120	100

The findings indicate that respondents have advocated for ICT facilities. The majority of the scholars, or 70 in total, chose internet-connected

laptops and desk tops. The fewest respondents, or n=5, favoured teleconferences and video conferencing for research.

Table 3.13 Purpose of Google Usage
120-Science-90 S.Science-30

S.No	Google Usage	Science (n = 90)			Social Sciences (n = 30)		
		Mean	SD	Rank	Mean	SD	Rank
1.	Google Simple	3.76	0.49	I	3.76	0.70	I
2.	Scholar	2.96	0.83	IV	2.95	0.86	IV
3.	Image	2.84	1.04	VI	3.04	0.80	V
4.	Book	3.10	0.87	II	2.71	1.10	VIII
5.	Videos	2.56	1.00	VII	3.23	0.83	III
6.	Translate	3.03	0.83	III	3.09	0.88	IV
7.	News	2.89	0.96	V	3.38	1.02	II
8.	Analytics	2.26	1.02	VIII	2.85	1.15	VII

The use of Google among social science and science research scholars was examined. The respondents gave Google Simple the top rating. On Google Images, among scientists, and Google Analytic,

among social scientists, a significant discrepancy was discovered.

Table 3.14, Source of Information on Internet

Source of Information		Science			Social Sciences		
		Mean	SD	Rank	Mean	SD	Rank
B1.	Open Access Articles	4.07	0.7	I	4.09	0.94	II
B2.	Open Access Books	3.34	1.15	III	3.80	1.28	III
B3.	YouTube Information	3.25	1.24	IV	4.14	0.85	I
B4.	Electronics Journal	3.45	1.09	II	3.66	1.39	V
B5.	Slide Share	3.45	1.39	II	3.76	1.09	IV
B6.	Electronic Conference	3.10	1.08	V	3.57	1.24	VI
B7.	Literature	3.34	1.01	III	3.80	1.32	III

The information on the internet usage by research scholars in the social sciences and sciences is indicated in the table above by the information source. Open access articles scored a mean of 4.07, placing them first among scientists, while YouTube scored a mean of 4.14, placing it first among social scientists.

Findings

1. The majority of students use the internet for email.
2. Three-fifths of academics choose Google as a search engine.
3. Students have computers with Internet access.
4. The majority of scholars in both the social sciences and the sciences use Simple Google.
5. Open access articles were determined to have the highest average among scientists, and YouTube information had the greatest average among social scientists for internet information sources.

Conclusion

Academic libraries now have a wealth of new, exciting possibilities thanks to electronic resources. The current state of information explosion makes it difficult to acquire knowledge. It is essential to inform them of the electronic resources available to scholars and to create a welcoming environment for them. It will also result in a greater degree of ICT utilisation. The large number of pupils using the internet to gather information provides evidence of its usefulness. The respondents are aware that using the internet to achieve conceptual clarity is a viable option.

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